

ISLAM IN DUNGAN CULTURE

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Annotation: This article focuses on the origin of the Dungan people, the concept of ethnocultural identity, the role of Islam in the formation of the Dungan people. At the same time, an attempt was made to shed light on the role of religion in the lives of Dungans and similar diasporas on the basis of comparative analysis.

The reasons why Islam, which once served as the most important marker of ethnocultural identity in the life of the Dungans, have given way to the Dungan language with the change of space have been revealed.

The role of Islam in the ethno-cultural identity of the Dungans of modern Central Asia, especially Uzbekistan, its differences between different categories of the Dungans and the reasons for these differences were discussed.

Keywords: identity, ethnocultural identity, culture, Islam, Dungans, Chinese, Hui.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ethnocultural identity is a complex socio-psychological phenomenon in which an individual expresses its identity with a particular ethnic community, which differs in different aspects of culture: language, customs, rituals, traditions, religion, etc., primarily as an individual and a collective.

Only a comprehensive analysis of the factors that make up ethnocultural identity as a whole can create a more complete and accurate understanding of it. Determining the place of Islam in the ethnocultural identity of the Dungan people serves for a correct and complete understanding of the culture of these people.

This article discusses the role of religion in the formation of ethnocultural identity and the role of Islam in Dungan ethnoculture. At the same time, an attempt was made to shed light on the role of religion in the lives of Dungans and similar diasporas on the basis of comparative analysis.

Besides them, research methods such as comparative analysis of relevant sources, observations, interviews as a result of field research were used.

Everyone can believe in religions or cannot believe in any religions at all. Regardless of these beliefs, of course, a person feels that he/she belongs to a certain group depending on the situation. Just as ethnocultural identity occurs in intercultural relations, religious identity is also manifested in the process of interreligious

communication. Religious identity is more stable and bounded than ethnic or cultural identity, and its transformation is much more complex.

Prior to the emergence of theories and ideas about nation and ethnicity, religion was an important indicator of the identity of the individual. In this context, the influence of religion on the formation of ethnic identity should be emphasized.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. The origin of the Dungan people

The Dungans call themselves "Huihui." The name is also found in Chinese sources in the same form. However, scientists do not have a concrete idea when this name appeared in Chinese sources [5]. According to some scientists, the name appeared during the empire of the Northern Sun (960-1126). Li Shen-ju, a historian of the Qing Dynasty (1644-1911), wrote in his "Study of the Geographical Part of the History of the Liao Dynasty" ("Liao Shi di chji kao") that after the Five Dynasties (907-960) "This means that from the time of the Five Dynasties in China, the term "Huihui" has appeared in historical sources. From the time of the Northern Sun dynasty (960-1126), the name "Huihui" began to appear more and more in documents [3]. During this period, the term Huihui meant the Arab caliphate, not the Chinese Dungans, and the state was also called in Chinese sources as "Dashi go" [7].

Since the Yuan Dynasty, Muslims from the Arab Caliphate had been referred to as "semu," meaning "other people," and "non-Chinese people," but the term is now used to as "huihui" or "hui." The term is used in China to refer to the newly formed Dungan people only at the end of the Yuan Dynasty or from the time of the Ming Dynasty (1368-1644).

During the Qing Dynasty, the term "Hanhui" appeared and meant "Chinese Muslims". The term was first clarified in a 1647 report by Gansu Province Governor Zhang Shan: "On the west side of the Yellow River, Din Go-lyan Muslim rebel leaders and others illegally elected Tuluntoy as their leader. According to reports from Suzhou, they have united several thousand "Muslims with headscarves" - "Chanhui", "Muslims in red hats", "Muslim aunts", "Hanhui" - Chinese Muslims and others. they were given various positions "(" A Brief History of Gansu, Ningxia and Qinghai Provinces "- " Gan Ning Qing Shilue "). However, Zhang Shan did not comment on the term "Hanhui" - "Chinese Muslims". For this reason, it is not possible to say exactly what national name the term was used for. Any ethnos is a product of history[15].

After 1911th revolution, the term "Hanhui" became widespread, and today the name is used to refer to Chinese Muslims. However, such thinking may be opposed to confusing the Dungans with the Chinese or the nation with religion, or with the Dungans 'views of the nation. However, it is not correct to accept them as just a religious community.

Although Islam is actually a religion, it has also become the name of a separate group in China. This name was originally used to distinguish them from the natives of China, but later became the name of a separate people [11].

In addition, the term "dungan" (dunganhui) was used by the Xinjiang Uyghurs, who called the dungans "dunganhui". Today, generations of several thousand Dungans have migrated to various parts of Central Asia as a result of the defeated Dungan uprising of the late 19th century. They are also called Dungan people, but their Chinese descendants do not and do not want to call themselves Dungans. The main part of the Dungans has spread to Central Asia and some minorities to many other parts of the world and live as a diaspora [10].

Thus, summarizing the above ideas, the origin of the Dungans is directly related to Islam and its infiltration into China, and their ethnogenesis involved not one, but several people. These are: the Arabs, the Persians, the Turkish population of Central Asia, the Turkish population of north-western China, and the original Chinese population. The unification of these people led to the emergence of a separate religious community and, on its basis, a separate people - the Dungans (Huey).

B. The role of religion in ethnocultural identity.

Researchers dealing with the history of diasporas have argued that the unity of religious views serves not only one diaspora but also the union or partial convergence of several such diasporas [13]. For example, the Greek Catholic Church played an important role in the unification of the various Ukrainian diasporas in Canada and Latin America. An important aspect of this example is that the religious factor is the reason for the rapprochement of the two separate diasporas. As noted above, religious identity is stronger than other types of identity.

It is worth mentioning the Armenians as another example in clearly showing the place of religion in the life of the diaspora and its duration. In the 5th century, the emergence of a new trend of Christianity among the Armenians called monophysitism and the consolidation of the ethnos around it became an important factor in the survival of the Armenian nation without being assimilated like the Jews in medieval conditions with very weak ethnic boundaries [14]. Of course, in doing so, boundaries were religiously held, and the aspect served as a key aspect in maintaining their identity.

In the Muslim diaspora, religion is an important aspect of the community's cohesion and longevity. This can also be seen in the example of the Dungans (Hui or Huizu) in China. Religion is the most important criterion for them to understand and maintain their identity. This is because Dungan and Chinese culture are separated by Islamic rules. It is very difficult to distinguish their culture from Chinese culture if the Dungans' belief in Islam is studied without regard.

There is no denying that local religious teachings also have an impact on Dungan culture. This can be seen in everything from examples of applied art to folklore. These

include the immortal heroes of fairy tales, magical and supernatural beings, and various sacred animals.

Alternatively, religion has a strong position in some diasporas and a less powerful one in others. This view can be substantiated by the fact that in a diaspora living in a foreign religious environment, while religion is an important marker for self-preservation, the importance of non-religious markers in a religious environment is higher. For example, V. Titov, who studied the Muscovite Assyrians. Commenting on their self-awareness, Titov writes that "historical memory, culture (folklore, music, holidays, ceremonies) and religion were one of the main factors in the identity of the diaspora" [12]. This is almost the case. This is because the Dungans and the local Muslim population are almost indistinguishable from each other in terms of religious beliefs, and therefore Islam cannot be a marker in their identity. At this point, language emerges as the most important marker of ethnocultural identity.

Undoubtedly, the most important role in the emergence and formation of the Dungan people is the spread of Islam in China. In 1910, the commander of the French army, Viscount d'Ollone, who was among the Huey, wrote in a report on what he saw there that "because of religion, the Huey are distinguished from the Khan as a different nation" [1].

The formation of Dungan culture has two bases, the first of which is ancient Chinese culture and the second is Islamic culture. It is on these two foundations that the unique Dungan culture was built. F. Commenting on the role of Islam in the life of the Dungans, Poyarkov wrote, "... in a word, Islam gave birth to the Dungans" [9]. With the above two examples, it can be seen that the formation of the Dungan people is the primary basis of Islam.

Although Chinese culture dominated the Dungan culture, some features of other earlier peoples also survived. In this regard, a well-known Kyrgyz Dungan scholar A. In his research on Dungan culture, John mentions a similar Turkmen tradition of not sending a new bride to his father's house for a month, which is present in some Dungan communities, and that this closeness also plays a role in the formation of Dungan people and culture.

The main basis for the new community that was being formed was, of course, its own religion, Islam. The community, formed on the basis of Islam, has formed a strong faith in the faith of this people through adherence to its religious beliefs as much as possible, adherence to religious boundaries, and strict adherence to the Islamic creed.

Thus, if ethnocultural identity can be understood as a sense of cultural belonging to an ethnos, then Islam served as the basis for the formation of the Dungans (Huey) as a people and their formation. As a result of the infiltration and spread of Islam in China, a new nation emerged there.

The Dungans distinguished themselves from the Chinese by their religious affiliation - religious identity, and this religious identity served as the main marker in their formation as a nation. In a word, the religious identity of the Dungans is the main marker of their ethnocultural identity.

C. A change in the identity marker in a new cultural environment.

Traditional Dungan society differs from neighboring Muslims in its religious beliefs by its somewhat firm adherence to the doctrinal issues of the religion. The reason for this is that they live in a non-religious environment, and as a rule, in a society where the vast majority of the community believes in another religion, the strong protection of their religion is important in maintaining the identity of this ethnic unit.

At the end of the 19th century, the Dungans revolted against the Qing Empire in China. The Dungan revolt of 1864–1877 ended in failure, and a section of the Dungans migrated to Central Asia. Changes in space and time have also changed the most basic marker of Dungan ethnocultural identity. This is because Islam, which played an important role in the formation of the Dungan (Huey) people, could no longer serve as an ethnic border with the peoples of Central Asia. As a result, in the new cultural environment, this task has been occupied first and foremost by various aspects of culture.

D. The ethnocultural identity of the Dungans of Uzbekistan in new research.

A diaspora may lose its language, customs and traditions, food and clothing, but losing its religion is a very rare occurrence.

The religious and sectarian unity of the Dungan diaspora with the local population led to their rapprochement and, in some cases, their assimilation. Given that the unity of religion is also the most important factor in marriage according to the rules of Islam, mixed marriages between the local Muslim population and the Dungans led to their intermingling. Mixed marriages are common in the predominantly Dungan city of Tashkent, and especially in Andijan.

There are three reasons why mixed marriages are prevalent in these two areas:

- First, Dungans live in these areas mixed with local Uzbeks;
- Second, as a result of long-term neighborliness, the borders with the Dungan and neighboring indigenous peoples have weakened their culture;
- Thirdly, as a result of the strong level of Uzbekization typical of the Dungans of Andijan, they feel closer to the local Uzbeks or Uyghurs than to the Dungans.

Identity is seen directly when a team or individual compares what they have with the same thing in another team or individual. The idea can be applied not only to religion, but also to culture and language. This idea was also reflected in field research. When asked, “Why preserve cultural identity and language?” Almost all respondents (93%) said that although they have no idea about identity, “you have to be “something” unique to Dungans”. [16]. In this question, what they say about "something" is mainly

focused on language, and in the Chinese Dungans, religion plays the role of "something" instead of language.

Interviews with Dungans and non-Dungans in the field research revealed that both Dungan society today and religious beliefs are stronger than the beliefs of the local population. This opinion was also witnessed by non-Dungan locals [16]. Indigenous Muslims came to this conclusion, of course, as a result of many years of observation and comparison of its results with their own beliefs.

Even on the basis of direct observation, it can be seen that religious traditions are much stronger in the Dungan family and in society as a whole. As a basis for this view, it can be argued that during field research, after talking to men in the family, women were often not allowed to do so if they wanted to talk as well. Another idea is that when a stranger enters the house, of course, the landlord appoints his family to be a "shelter" from his family, which has been observed many times during field research [17].

It is well known that religion in turn is life. If this idea is explained more broadly, religion encompasses all parts of human life: birth, upbringing, growth, nutrition, marriage, childbearing, and death. Religious rules interact with the pre-religious culture of the community and adapt to each other, leading to the formation of a specific culture. That is, if a nation adopts a new religion, it will certainly adapt some aspects of its traditional religious culture to the new religion. For example, in some Central Asian nations, such rituals as **Bibiseshanbe** and **Bibichorshanbe** are not actually related to Islam, but some elements of Buddhism, Taoism, and Confucianism have survived in various forms of applied art and folklore. [6].

The influx of Islam into China in various ways has led to the emergence of almost a few sectarian representatives there. However, the Dungans who migrated to Central Asia adapted to the sects of the indigenous people.

III. CONCLUSION

As a result of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

- The most important factor in the formation of the Dungan (Hui) people was the Islamic factor and, in connection with this, the population that came to China from various Muslim countries. On this basis, new Dungan (Xui) people were formed in China;

- Before the emergence of the concept of national and ethnic identity, religion was the main marker of identity;

- While religious identity is the primary factor for an ethnos in a other religious society, other elements of culture serve as the primary factor in a religious society;

- The differences in the culture of the Dungans, who live compactly in the territory of Uzbekistan, and the Dungans, who live scattered, are due to the remoteness from the cultural core and the lack of contacts;

- With the migration of the Dungans to Central Asia, the peculiarities of their culture became the basis of identity;

- The declining role of religion in the ethnocultural identity of the Dungans and the gradual decline of their culture are likely to lead them to assimilate and assimilate into the Muslims of Central Asia as a minority ethnos. For this reason, in modern society, Central Asian Dungans, especially Uzbek, should strive to preserve their linguistic and cultural identity as much as possible.

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